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Research Article

**BEHAVIOR OF MEDICAL STUDENTS TOWARDS THE
PATIENTS OF LEUKEMIA & AIDS**¹Dr Muhammad Adeel Basharat, ²Dr Muhammad Tanveer, ³Dr Malik Zeeshan
¹Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan.**Article Received:** December 2018 **Accepted:** February 2019 **Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of this study was to know about the behavior of students of medical field to the patients suffering with leukemia versus patients of AIDS.

Methodology: This transverse research work was based on non-probability sampling method. Two hundred and five medical students were the participants of this research work. The duration of this research work was from July 2017 to October 2018. The measurement of prejudicial behaviors and consent to work together carried out on the basis of a little written description on four case with the utilization of PES (Prejudicial Evaluation Scale) & SIS (Social Interaction Scale). SPSS software version seventeen was in use for the analysis of the data. T test was in use for the calculation of the disparities among the average inventory score & every inventory item. Paired T test was in use for the analysis of the disparity in the behavior of the students of medical field after & before attending the medical institute.

Results: Very high significant disparities were available in the behavior of medical students concluded by the general average scores of responses to the patients suffering with AIDS (44.45 ± 9.32) & (24.22 ± 11.69) versus patients of leukemia (49.65 ± 10.73) & (20.67 ± 7.84) of prejudicial evaluation scale & social interaction scale Inventories correspondingly. The comparison on these scales for every item on both of these scales concluded various items to be different for patients suffering with AIDS versus patients of Leukemia displaying negative bias to the group of stigmatization.

Conclusions: The medical students found with negative prejudice for the patients suffering with AIDS & stated much lower consent to work together with AIDS in comparison with the patients suffering with the patients of leukemia.

Keywords: Inventories, Medical Students, Stigmatization, Disparity, Leukemia Epidemics.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pakistan has started to face the occurrence & confront the disease of AIDS [1]. The 1st full-grown HIV outbreak was faced in the year of 2004 [2] followed by epidemics in the whole nation [3]. IVDAs (Intravenous drug abusers), workers of the sex field, sex with same sex are the high risk people for the spread of this disease in our country [1, 4]. According to the estimation of UNAIDS, ninety thousand people were present with this disease in our country in 2009. Total occurrence of this disease is low, IVDAs are mostly the victims of HIV & this disease is also occurring in transgender in some areas of our country. In 2008, the occurrence of HIV among intravenous drug abusers IVDAs ranged from ten to three hundred percent across Faisalabad, Quetta, Karachi & Sargodha [3].

The discrimination has overshadowed the treatment against the treatment of the disease of AIDS in the whole world. The main fact is that the providers of the health service are the first to have contact with the patients of AIDS. The attitude & behavior of discrimination as displayed by the professionals of the health care towards the patients of AIDS have expressed the bad results on their QoL (quality of life) & this is also the outcome of many research works [5-7]. The measurement of the stigma of HIV is not easy [8]. Kelly & his colleagues [9] utilized the short written descriptions of cases to evaluate the attitudes of the doctors towards the patients of AIDS in the year of 1987. The analytical worth of the behavior of doctor has supported the case vignettes to gain the success over the years [10-12].

Kelly [9] had found a less consent to cooperate with the patients of AIDS in comparison with the patients of the leukemia [13]. A research work from Japan utilized the same vignettes & concluded that significant disparities in the students of university towards the patients of such diseases [14].

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work conducted on the students of 3rd, 4th and 5th years of Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan. The duration of this research work was from July 2017 to October 2018. A non-probable sampling technique used for the selection of two hundred and five medical students. The students from each college were more than sixty. Out of two hundred and forty-nine anonymously managed questionnaires, two hundred and ten questionnaires returned back with a rate of response of 84.3%. Rejection of 5 questionnaires carried out due to multiple selections.

Every student received a vignette of five hundred words about a patient. He was a patient of chronic, debilitating disease. Every student read the identical vignettes except that the disease was Aids or either leukemia in the vignettes. The possible scenarios were available after that. After reading that student have to answer their attitudes. The selection of the instrument carried out from the original research work of Kelly [9]. SPSS .17 was in use for the analysis of collected data. T test was in use for the analysis of the average disparities linked with the condition of the disease of the patient. The disparities of the items on individual basis carried out with the utilization of the student's T tests.

RESULTS:

One hundred and eighty-nine students were from sixteen to twenty-five year of age. One hundred and eighteen participants were females and 87 were male participants. Fifty percent students claimed that they had a focused study of AIDS during their course of study; of which nineteen students had done courses on AIDS, seventy-one were the participants of the associated course, and twelve students got knowledge through seminars while eleven students go knowledge from other resources as television, magazines, and internet. The particular disparities among average responses for individual objects in PES were resolute as mentioned in Table-1.

Scale	Arshad with AIDS		Majid with Leukemia		p value*
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
PES	44.450	9.32	49.65	9.87	<0.001*

*Students' t test significant at <0.05, p<0.01= very significant, p<0.001 = highly significant

Kelly made 2 groups as AIDS & leukemia in his research work. The comparison of both studies conducted. The averages of all items in both of the results are added and the T test used for the analysis of the statistical disparity as described in Table-1.

Students' T test was in use to find out the statistical importance of the average disparity of the individual objects in the PES & SIS-R. Some objects displayed statistically significant disparities of averages within both inventories (Table-2 & Table-3).

Table-II: Prejudicial Evaluation Scale (PES) t test Findings

		AIDS		Leukemia		95% CI	p value*
		Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD		
1	Arshad is responsible for his illness.	2.54	1.61	3.78	2.18	-1.770, -0.710	<0.0010
2	Arshad deserves sympathy and understanding.	3.07	2.16	2.47	1.53	0.090, 1.120	<0.0100
3	Arshad deserves what has happened to him.	3.74	1.96	4.51	2.02	-1.320, -0.230	<0.0010
4	Arshad is dangerous to other people.	2.59	1.6	4.59	1.85	-2.480, -1.520	<0.0010
5	Arshad deserves the best medical care possible.	2.28	1.75	1.69	1.34	0.170, 1.020	0.0070
6	Deserves to die	5.06	2.22	5.94	1.59	-1.140, -0.350	<0.0010
7	The World would be better off without Arshad	4.61	2.4	5.71	1.62	-1.670, -0.540	<0.0010

8	Suicide might be the best solution for Arshad	5.72	2.03	5.91	1.72	-0.710, 0.320	0.4600
9	Arshad Should be quarantined so he doesn't expose	4.27	2.2	4.67	2.28	-1.010, 0.220	0.2070
10	Arshad deserves to lose his job	5.44	2.04	5.46	1.98	-0.570, 0.540	0.9510

*Students' t test significant at <0.05, p<0.01= very significant, p< 0.001 = highly significant

Table-III: SIS T test Findings

		AIDS		Leukemia		95% CI	p value*
		Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD		
1	Would you be willing to take on Arshad as a psychotherapy client?	3.500	2.000	2.250	1.400	0.780, 1.730	<0.0010
2	If you met Arshad would you be willing to strike up a conversation with him?	2.930	1.980	2.430	1.300	0.040, 0.960	<0.0100
3	Would you be willing to work in the same office as Arshad?	2.780	1.800	2.600	1.410	-0.260, 0.620	0.426
4	Would you attend a party where Arshad was preparing food?	3.310	1.940	3.130	1.560	-0.310, 0.660	0.47

5	Would you attend a party where Arshad was present?	2.440	1.600	2.440	1.230	-0.390, 0.390	0.9920
6	Would you allow your children to visit Arshad in his home?	3.760	2.100	3.360	1.660	-0.120, 0.920	0.134
7	If you were a friend of Arshad's, would you be willing to continue the friendship at this time?	2.420	1.770	2.060	1.210	- 0.050, 0.780	<0.0010
8	Arshad's lease is up in two months. If you were his landlord, would you renew his lease?	3.080	1.910	2.410	1.490	0.200, 1.140	<0.0010

DISCUSSION:

The behavior of the people towards the patients of AIDS is a social issue. But the behavior of the future doctors about the patients of AIDS may carry valuable implications of the health care. It is stated that even the providers of the health care carry emotional charge & elicits judgmental, bad assessments about the diagnosis of AIDS patients. This kind of behavior shows that majority of doctors feel uneasiness while treating the patients of AIDS which hinder the optimistic, constructive & association between doctor and patient of AIDS. This research work is in favor with the outcomes of other case studies that has concluded that a small written description is a very reliable tool for the measurement of the people of different occupations & having background from various cultures towards the patients suffering with various diseases.

Majority of patients believed that the patient of AIDS is not a danger for the other people but he deserves not live and he can leave the world safer without him. These finding are very close to the results of

McGrory [15] who discovered the same attitude in the students of medical field of studying at Columbian University located in New York. Li L [16] stated same outcomes working on the health professional of China. Kelly [9, 17] and Crawford I [18] concluded the same behaviors of the doctors & medical students while utilizing the same vignettes. Majority of the professionals of medical field links the patients of AIDS with the groups of IVDA's & sex workers.

The outcomes about the behavior toward homosexuals are similar with the other research works which have concluded dental health did not show a prejudice toward the homosexuals [19, 20]. There is a need of immediate attention & special concern for the making of new policy & management in the setting of the health care to handle the potential prejudices of providers of the health care field. This research work was only conducted on the students so the findings of this research work cannot be generalized. Research works on large variety of samples in the whole country including the

professionals are the requirement to know about the realities of the problem of AIDS.

CONCLUSIONS:

Formal education about sex & lectures on the awareness about AIDS should be the main ingredient of the main curriculums. Print media as well as various forms of electronic media can play an important role in the making of people full aware of the ways of the spread of this disease & prevention steps against this disease.

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